

Effect Of Metal Pollutants on Hemocytes of Freshwater Molluscs, *Bellamyia bengalensis*: The Reliable Markers of Aquatic Pollution

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Abstract

Hemocytes are useful tool for assessing the toxicity of heavy metals on freshwater gastropods. Freshwater molluscs *Bellamyia bengalensis* were exposed to sodium arsenite (NaAsO₂), mercury (II) chloride (HgCl₂), lead nitrate, zinc sulphate and copper sulphate (CuSO₄.5H₂O) for the different exposure periods as 24hrs, 48hrs, 72hrs and 96hrs. Control specimens were untreated by any toxic metals. Hemolymph was collected and hemocytes were stained by Giemsa, Leishmans Eosin Methylene blue solution, neutral red and trypan blue. Results showed that heavy metal toxicity affected the morphology and function of chief immune effector cells (hemocytes) in freshwater molluscs and also inhibited the degree of hemocyte aggregation, clot formation which may affect “encapsulation response”, microaggregation and wound healing. Cells showed neutral red (NR) positive reaction in cytoplasm indicating damage of lysosomal membrane due to metal toxicity. Mortality index was also significantly increased in 96hrs of treated group. This supports the idea that hemocyte analysis is a reliable tool to obtain information about pollution which may act as markers of aquatic biomonitoring approach.

Keywords

Hemocytes, Aggregation, Freshwater gastropods, Environmental pollution

INTRODUCTION

A global concern about the role of heavy metals in aquaculture has been raised due to health risks for consumers (Lakra and Nagpure, 2009). The ecotoxicological assessment is essential to identify potential environmental risk. Hemocytes are useful tool for assessing the toxicity of heavy metals, and pesticides on aquatic invertebrates like freshwater gastropods. Researchers showed that aquatic animals like benthic oligochaetes, gastropods, insects, crustaceans, fishes are more sensitive to ecological risk of heavy metal pollution (Ishrat, 2020). Hemocyte analysis of freshwater molluscs

Bellamyia bengalensis could be used as effective biomarkers for evaluation of environmental pollution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The snails *B. bengalensis* were collected in the early morning from some selective ponds during November- December 2024. A total 80 *B. bengalensis* were collected by handpicking. They were then transported to laboratory. They were acclimatized in glass aquaria for 3 days to laboratory regimes before experimentation. Freshwater molluscs *Bellamyia bengalensis* were exposed to sodium arsenite

(NaAsO₂) in water at 0.025 mg/L (group 1), mercury (II) chloride (HgCl₂) in water at 0.30 mg/L (group 2), lead nitrate in water medium at 50 mg/L (group 3), zinc sulphate at 0.43 mg/L in glass aquaria (group 4) and copper sulphate (CuSO₄.5H₂O) at 0.56 ppm (group 5) for the different exposure periods as 24hrs, 48hrs, 72hrs and 96hrs. Control specimens were untreated by any toxic metals (Each group, n=6) (after Guria, 2020; Guria, 2023; Guria and Ali, 2024; Kamble and Kamble, 2012).

Hemolymph was collected from *B. bengalensis* and smeared on glass slides and stained by Giemsa, Leishmans Eosin Methylene blue solution, neutral red and observed under light microscope. Cell viability test was done by trypan blue assay. Cell counting was performed by hemocytometer.

RESULT

A clotting formation on glass slides by granulocytes was found in control molluscs (Fig. 1). Hemocytes fused together to form clots or cell clumps. Small clumps of cells then aggregated to form larger masses. The aggregation of molluscs by hemocytes in vitro can be categorized into weak aggregation and cohesive aggregation (Fig. 1). Significant number of cells became pyknotic after treatment (Fig. 2, 4, 6 and 12).

As, Hg, Pb, Zn, Cu inhibited the degree of hemocyte aggregation, clot formation. Mean number of compact aggregates was found to be less after 24 hrs, 48hrs, 72hrs and 96hrs of metal treatment. Mean number of cells in each clump/ aggregate was also decreased after 48hrs, 72hrs and 96hrs of metal treatment which may affect “encapsulation response”, microaggregation and wound healing (Fig. 8, 9, 10 and 11).

As and Hg treated cells showed neutral red (NR) positive response in their cytoplasm indicating damage of lysosomal membrane leading to the release of hydrolases in the cytoplasm (Fig. 3).

The cytosol of granular hemocytes were rich in carbohydrates (PAS positive) in control animals. But the mean percentage of Periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) positive cells became less in treated animals after 72hrs and 96hrs of treatment of Hg (Fig. 7).

The percentage of Trypan Blue (TB) positive cells represented a mortality index which was significantly increased in 96hrs of treated group (P value < 0.0001) (Fig. 5 and 13).

Increased roundness of the immune cells with decreased number of pseudopods in hemocytes after Hg treatment was noted (Fig. 14)

Fig. 1. Control hemocytes showed different stages of clotting formation (x400). A clotting formation from beginning (cell fusion, weak aggregation) to complete process (cohesive aggregation, clotting formation) to show a central point surrounding with numerous granulocytes.

Fig. 2. Leishmans Eosin Methylene blue solution stained pyknotic cells/ necrotic cells in arsenic (As) treated group in 24 hrs (A), 48hrs condition (B), and 72hrs condition (C), and 96hrs condition (D) (x 400) (indicated by arrow) PC=Pyknotic cells, NC=Necrotic cells

Fig. 3. Neutral Red stained control *Bellamyia* hemocytes (A), Neutral Red stained *Bellamyia* hemocytes in arsenic treated group in 48hrs condition (B), and in Hg treated group in 72hrs condition (C) and cell rupture indicated by arrow (x 400) PC=Pyknotic cells, NC=Necrotic cells

Fig. 4. Leishmans Eosin Methylene blue solution stained pyknotic cells/ necrotic cells in mercury (Hg) treated group in 48 hrs (A) and Giemsa stained pyknotic cells in Hg treated group in 72hrs condition (B) (indicated by arrow) PC=Pyknotic cells, NC=Necrotic cells

Fig. 5. Trypan blue stained cells in control group (indicated by red arrow) (A) and Trypan blue stained cells in copper sulphate treated group in 72hrs condition (B) (indicated by black arrow)

Fig. 6. Leishmans Eosin Methylene blue solution stained pyknotic cells/ necrotic cells in ZnSo4 treated group in 48 hrs (A), 72 hrs condition (B), and 96 hrs condition (C) (x 400) (indicated by arrow)
PC=Pyknotic cells

Fig. 7. A=SGH (small granular hemocytes) and LGH (large granular hemocytes) (periodic acid Schiff (PAS)-positive) in control animals, B= PAS positive cells after 72hrs of Hg treatment PAS positive cells- indicated by black arrows, PAS negative cells-indicated by red arrows.

Fig.8. Mean number of cells within aggregates after metal treatment noticed on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value =0.0003).

Fig.9. Mean number of cell aggregates after Hg treatment noticed on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value =0.0009).

Fig. 10. Mean number of cell aggregates after As treatment noticed on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value =0.0003).

Fig.11. Mean number of cell aggregates after Zn treatment noticed on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value =0.0115).

Fig. 12. Mean number of pyknotic cells on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value= 0.0224).

Fig. 13. Mean mortality index after metal treatment noticed on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value < 0.0001).

Fig.14. Mean number of round immune cells after Hg treatment on glass slides. Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM. P-Value < 0.05 is considered to be statistically significant (ANOVA, P value < 0.0001).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The defense mechanisms of molluscs involve hemocytes performing cellular reactions like phagocytosis, nodule formation, encapsulation. Encapsulation is caused by infiltration and aggregation of hemocytes at the site of infection. Pollutants can affect biological cycles of aquatic organisms (Khayat-zadeh and Abbasi, 2010).

Copper sulphate is used as algicide or herbicide for the control of phytoplankton or weeds in aquatic bodies (Watson and Yanong, 2002). In copper treated group of *Filopaludina bengalensis*, increased mucus secretion (%) and decreased foot protrusion was noted (Ghosh *et al.*, 2021). Guria (2020) revealed cellular death of hemocytes of *Pila* sp. after treatment with arsenic. Guria (2023) indicated cytoplasmic vacuolation and membrane blebbing of hemocytes in *Bellamya bengalensis*, after lead (Pb) exposure.

Many workers studied mercurial compounds toxicity to aquatic animals (Rehowldt *et al.*, 1973). Eldon *et al.*, (1980) studied the effect of low concentration of heavy metals on the bivalve, *Macoma balthica* and observed that mortality was high on in animals exposed to Hg and Cd. Methylmercury form of mercury is a concern because it is absorbed easily into the food chain. Necrosis, vacuolation and degeneration of hepatocytes were observed when *Channa punctatus* was exposed to mercuric chloride for 30 days (Sastry and Gupta, 1978; Rani and Ramamurthi, 1989). Rana and Sharma (1982) observed mercurial toxicity in the liver of a freshwater teleost, *Channa punctatus*. Greater accumulation of Hg in liver after a longer treatment and the respective change in enzyme activity showed a close response relationship. Mercury exposition on filter feeder molluscs induced structural changes and permeability in cell membrane, alteration in a number of enzymatic reactions and imbalance in the

levels of vital inorganic cations (Sivaramakrishna and Radhakrishnaiah, 2000). Mussels showed a higher capacity for mercury (Hg) accumulation compared to oyster and clams (Briant *et al.*, 2017). Previous papers reported exposure to Hg increased roundness of the immune cells due to less pseudopods in hemocytes of mussels and snails (Marchi *et al.*, 2004; Leomanni *et al.*, 2016). Also, sub-lethal methylmercury concentration induced immunosuppression in ascidian *Styela plicata*, (Cammarata *et al.*, 2007). The effects of LC50/10 concentrations of mercuric chloride on histology of hepatopancreas have been documented by some researchers in *Bellamya bengalensis* (Mahajan., 2023). The histopathological alterations included damaged epithelial cells and disruption of hepatic tubules at 0.109 ppm HgCl₂ for 7 days.

Parisi *et al.*, (2021) showed methyl mercury (CH₃HgCl) promoted the alteration of hemocyte viability, modification of the morphological features and cellular spreading of the mussel, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*.

Pagano *et al.*, 2017 showed the effects of two heavy metals (CdCl₂ and ZnCl₂) on digestive glands and haemolymph of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* which caused damage to haemocytes and digestive cells, mainly after 7 days of exposure.

Belal and Gad, 2023 showed that zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO-NPs) at concentrations of 50 and 100 µg/ml have significantly decreased the total hemocyte count (THC) and different hemocyte count (DHC) except the number of oenocytes as they were significantly increased in 5th larval instar of *Bombyx mori*. It caused morphological deformities like loss of pseudopods and destroyed cell membranes, nuclear degeneration, cytoplasmic lysis, and appearance of cytoplasmic vacuoles.

Present results showed that heavy metal toxicity has affected the morphology and function of chief

immune effector cells (hemocytes) in freshwater molluscs and also inhibited the degree of hemocyte aggregation, clot formation which may affect “encapsulation response”, microaggregation and wound healing. Cells showed neutral red (NR) positive reaction in cytoplasm indicating damage of lysosomal membrane due to metal toxicity. Mortality index was also significantly increased in 96hrs of treated group. These results corroborated the previous researches.

This supports the idea that hemocyte analysis is a reliable tool to obtain information about pollution. Therefore, comprehensive research on aquatic bodies is necessary to identify the bioindicators which are essential to address the environmental challenges.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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